

ASSESSMENT OF COMMUNITY-BASED TRAINING (CBT) GRADUATES AMONG TESDA TECHNOLOGY INSTITUTIONS IN MARINDUQUE FOR C.Y. 2018-2022

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ABSTRACT

Community-based training goes further than just mere skills training provision. This study aims to assess community-based (CBT) program graduates among TESDA Technology Institutions in Marinduque for C.Y. 2018 to 2022. Specifically, this aims to determine the employment background of the community-based training graduates; identify the relevance of the skills acquired from community-based training; enumerate the perceived suggestions of graduates and employers to enhance the program further, and propose interventions. The research used a mixed design with a validated research questionnaire administered to graduates using a systematized sampling. Results reveal that most CBT graduates are unemployed and most employed are in the government sector. The majority of the self-employed employees are engaged in the whole retail business sector while the main reason for unemployment is the lack of job opportunities. The skills acquired by the CBT graduates are relevant to their job while problem-solving and critical thinking skills can improve their relevance. The employers evaluated the attitude as the highest among the three (3) assessed parameters, leaving skills and knowledge. However, improvements can be made in the three (3) aspects of learning. Graduates and employers highly suggested interventions in three major areas - the curriculum, industry-related matters, and CBT enhancement through stakeholder engagement. The interventions suggested to address this study's key findings highlight the development of a career placement center in the institutions, collaboration of industry partners and local government, stakeholder engagement, increase of training hours, and development of a comprehensive job placement program.

Keywords: *Community-based training, employment, graduates, TESDA*

INTRODUCTION

Throughout history, Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) has served as a crucial bridge between individuals and a fulfilling career path. By equipping young people and adults with the skills and knowledge they need, TVET empowers them to improve their quality of life (National Center for Education Statistics (2019)). This transformative potential has garnered increasing global attention, particularly for its ability to boost the productivity and income of disadvantaged individuals, enhance employability, and open doors to new job opportunities (Orbeta & Esguerra, 2016; UNESCO, 2016).

Assessment of community-based training graduates of Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programs is crucial for understanding the impact and effectiveness of these initiatives. Evaluation helps assess the relevance of acquired skills, employability, and workforce contribution. It provides insights into program effectiveness, highlights areas for improvement, and guides curriculum development. Effective evaluation leads to better job market preparation, increased employment opportunities, and economic growth. Without evaluation, graduates may be ill-prepared, leading to skills mismatches and limited socio-economic development. Studying assessment is essential for enhancing TVET programs, benefiting graduates, industries, communities, and society (Tripney & Hombrados, 2013).

Community-based training programs focus on the needs of local communities, such as out-of-school youth, women, unemployed adults, marginalized populations, indigenous people, and informal sector members. TESDA provides technical assistance, including training modules, equipment, supplies, qualified trainers, venue approvals, competency assessments, and certifications. TESDA also monitors and evaluates programs, co-signs training certificates, and facilitates the provision of starter tool kits to graduates (Robinson, 2012).

Community-based TVET programs empower individuals and communities by providing accessible training opportunities. These programs, implemented in collaboration with local government units, NGOs, and community organizations, address specific skill requirements and enhance livelihood opportunities. Assessing graduates at the local level identifies community-specific needs, measures the impact on local economies, and evaluates the effectiveness of skill development initiatives in grassroots development.

The TESDA Women's Center Tracer Study by Ignacio and Tabu (2018) reveals that over half of employed TVET graduates work full-time in the formal sector, with hospitality, food service, and construction being major employment destinations. A separate study by Mariano & Tantoco (2023) found an even higher employment rate of 87.94% among TVET graduates.

Overall, community-based training in TESDA empowers local communities through accessible and tailored skill development programs, contributing to economic growth, self-sufficiency, and the well-being of individuals within these communities.

Researches has highlighted concerns about the current state of Work Readiness in TVET graduates. The Asian Development Bank (2021) and Fletcher (2012) underscore the critical role of job skills and Work Readiness in determining graduate success. However, studies like Wibowo and Saptono (2018) point out that some vocational high schools might not be fully equipped to nurture these qualities in their students.

Gaps in community-based training graduates contribute to low employment rates include skills mismatches, limited industry relevance, lack of soft skills, and limited access to job opportunities. Addressing these gaps requires aligning programs with industry needs, incorporating soft skills development, providing job placement services, fostering entrepreneurship, and addressing economic factors. Collaboration between stakeholders is crucial.

Research Questions

This study seeks to assess graduates of the Community-Based Training (CBT) Program from TESDA Technology Institutions in Marinduque for C.Y. 2018 – 2022. Specifically, this is sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the employment background of the community-based training graduates in terms of:
 - 1.1 Employment Status
 - 1.2 Status of Employed Graduates
 - 1.2.1 Nature of Employment
 - 1.2.2 Employer Background/ Employment after Graduation
 - 1.2.3 Monthly Gross Income
 - 1.3 Entrepreneurial Status
 - 1.3.1 Nature of Business
 - 1.3.2 Length of Venturing into Business After Graduation
 - 1.3.3 Gross Income
2. What is the relevance of the skills acquired from community-based training to the graduates' current employment or entrepreneurial ventures?
3. How do employers assess the graduates of the community-based training in terms of:
 - 3.1 Knowledge
 - 3.2 Skills
 - 3.3 Attitudes
4. What are the graduates' and employers' suggestions to enhance TESDA community-based training programs in Marinduque?

METHODOLOGY

The study was mainly conducted in the province of Marinduque, specifically in the municipalities of Sta Cruz and Torrijos, where the selected TVET Institutions are located and CBT Programs are being implemented.

This study focused on graduates from two TESDA Technology Institutions (TTIs) in Marinduque who completed their training between 2018 and 2022. It employed a simple random sampling technique to choose a representative sample from this group. This method entails assigning a unique identification number to each eligible graduate and randomly selecting a set number of graduates for the study. By ensuring an equal opportunity for every graduate to be included in the sample, the study can effectively capture this specific cohort's unique perspectives and experiences. Utilizing simple random sampling minimizes bias and improves the applicability of the study findings to the wider population of graduates from these institutions within the specified timeframe. 304 respondents were selected from the 1440 graduates of the various programs.

Furthermore, the researcher also purposively and conveniently selected 15 TESDA industry partners who employed graduates of the CBT Program from TPSAT and BSAT from 2018 to 2022. This is to create further a relevant and accurate assessment of the graduates using the point of view of an employer.

In this study, the researcher used two self-made survey questionnaires explicitly designed for CBT graduates and the other for industry partners which was validated by the stakeholders (representatives from TESDA and specialist) The researcher also incorporated the TESDA tracer study questionnaire (2019) as a guide in drafting the self-made questionnaires as instruments for gathering the data needed in this study.

The data collection involved multiple methods. The researcher utilized survey questionnaires, which were distributed to respondents via Google Forms, and email. Additionally, the researcher personally visited the institutions to gather data by directly answering the questionnaires. Supplementary data gathering took place through the courtesy of the TESDA Technology Institutions in Marinduque, utilizing their existing database. Overall, the researcher obtained data from the TESDA Technology Institution database, conducted surveys through various means, and incorporated supplementary data from the TESDA Technology Institutions in Marinduque, thereby ensuring a comprehensive approach to gathering information on the community-based training graduates in the selected TESDA Schools.

The collected data underwent statistical analysis using standard statistical tools. The Likert scale was utilized for quantitative data to translate qualitative responses into numerical values.

RESULTS

Employment Background of the Community-Based Training Graduates

The different employment backgrounds of the Community-Based Training Graduates were gathered in this study and presented in the succeeding subsections.

Employment Status

Table 1 presents data on the employment status of individuals based on different programs. It shows the frequency and percentage of individuals employed, self-employed, and unemployed for each program.

Table 1. Employment Status of the Community-Based Training Graduates

PROGRAM	EMPLOYED		SELF EMPLOYED		UNEMPLOYED		Total	
	Freq	%age	Freq	%age	Freq	%age	Freq	%age
BPP NC II	0	0.00%	6	1.97%	10	3.29%	16	5.26%
CSS NC II	12	3.95%	4	1.32%	8	2.63%	24	7.89%
DomRAC NC II	2	0.66%	5	1.64%	8	2.63%	15	4.93%
DRIVING NC II	6	1.97%	1	0.33%	8	2.63%	15	4.93%
EIM NC II	0	0.00%	0	0.00%	16	5.26%	16	5.26%
EIM NC III	6	1.97%	4	1.32%	0	0.00%	10	3.29%
FOP NC II	0	0.00%	11	3.62%	12	3.95%	23	7.57%
GTAW NC II	8	2.63%	2	0.66%	11	3.62%	21	6.91%
OAP NC II	4	1.32%	7	2.30%	15	4.93%	26	8.55%
SMAW NC I	18	5.92%	8	2.63%	28	9.21%	54	17.76%
SMAW NC II	19	6.25%	5	1.64%	60	19.74%	84	27.63%
TOTAL	75	24.67%	53	17.43%	176	57.89%	304	100.00%

Out of the 304 individuals included in the analysis, 24.67% (75 individuals) are employed, 17.43% (53 individuals) are self-employed, and 57.89% (176 individuals) are unemployed. Some programs, such as SMAW NC II and SMAW NC I, have higher total counts, with 84 (72.63%) and 54 (17.76) individuals respectively. However, the majority of individuals within these programs are unemployed. This highlights the need to address graduates' employment challenges from these programs. It is encouraging that some individuals are self-employed, indicating their entrepreneurial endeavors. However, the overall percentage of self-employed individuals is relatively low compared to the unemployed population. Overall, the data is aligned to the study of the National Governors Association (2021) that efforts are needed to improve the employment outcomes for graduates across all programs. This could involve enhancing job placement services, fostering entrepreneurial skills, and addressing the factors contributing to the high unemployment rate among graduates.

Status of Employed Graduates

Table 2 shows the background of employed graduates in terms of the nature of employment.

Table 2. Nature of Employment of the Community-Based Training Graduates

Nature of Employment	Frequency	Percentage
Permanent	42	56.00%
Contractual	23	30.67%
Job Order	10	13.33%
Total	75	100.00%

It indicates that 56.00% of the employed graduates have permanent job positions. Graduates in permanent jobs usually have stability, benefits, and work security. It shows that a significant portion of workers have permanent jobs, which is encouraging for job security and professional advancement.

In terms of the nature of employment, contractual work makes up 30.67%. Contractual jobs often have a set duration and cannot provide the same security and perks as permanent work. The existence of contractual employment raises the possibility that businesses take advantage of this kind of labor for short-term or project-specific positions.

Furthermore, Job Order employment accounts for 13.33% of all employed graduates. Job order work is frequently project-based and transient, with employees hired for a particular assignment or duration. It shows a lower percentage of workers in contract and temporary positions than in permanent jobs.

In conclusion, majority of workers have permanent positions, indicating a stable workforce with long-term commitments. Contract and job order employment, however less in percentage, can provide organizations with flexibility for short-term needs.

Table 3 shows the employer background of the CBT graduates. The data on employer background reveals that private establishments, with a frequency of 44 and a percentage of 58.67%, have surpassed government employers, making them the predominant type of employer in the dataset.

Table 3. Employer Background of the Community-Based Training Graduates

Employer Background	Frequency	Percentage
Government	31	41.33%
Private Establishment	44	58.67%
Total	75	100.00%

The data presented in Table 3 indicates that private establishments are emerging as the predominant type of employer in the dataset. The higher frequency and percentage of private establishment employers compared to government employers indicate a growing reliance on the private sector for employment opportunities. This trend suggests a potential shift towards private sector job opportunities within the surveyed sample, reflecting the dynamic nature of the job market and the evolving balance between public

and private sector employment options. The data underscores the importance of monitoring these trends to understand the changing dynamics of the job market and the implications for individuals seeking employment in government and private establishments.

Table 3 shows the duration of employment of community-based training graduates after graduation. This data provides valuable insights into the timeline of employment outcomes for community-based training graduates, indicating varying durations for securing employment post-graduation. It underscores the importance of tracking and understanding the transition of graduates into the workforce to assess the effectiveness of the training programs and support services provided.

Table 4. Duration of Employment after Graduation

Employment After Graduation	Frequency	Percentage
Within 1 to 3 months	35	46.67%
Within 4 to 6 months	0	0.00%
After 6 months	5	6.67%
After 1 Year	31	41.33%
More than 2 Years	2	2.67%
No answer	2	2.67%
Total	75	100.00%

Most employed graduates, accounting for 46.67%, secured employment within the first three months after graduation. It indicates a fast transition from education to the workforce for a significant portion of the graduates. Finding employment within this timeframe is considered favorable as it reflects a proactive approach to entering the job market.

Almost 41.33% of graduates found employment within one year after completing their training. While not immediate, securing a job within the first year is still a positive outcome and suggests persistence in the job search process. This category represents a substantial portion of graduates who took a bit longer to enter the workforce but eventually found employment. A smaller percentage of 6.67% of graduates obtained employment after six months of graduation. This group may have faced challenges in finding suitable opportunities immediately after completing their studies. The delay in employment for this segment could be due to various factors such as market conditions or personal circumstances.

A very small percentage of graduates, 2.67% each, took more than two years to secure employment or did not respond. Graduates in these categories may have faced prolonged job search periods or chosen to pursue further education or other paths before entering the workforce. The data reflects a diverse timeline of employment outcomes for graduates, with varying durations to secure jobs after graduation.

Table 5 presents the monthly gross income of community-based training graduates. This data showcases the earnings of individuals who have completed community-based training programs. The table may provide insights into the income distribution among these graduates, highlighting the range of earnings they receive every month. Analyzing this data can offer valuable information on the financial outcomes of individuals who have undergone community-based training, shedding light on their economic status and potential financial stability.

Table 5. The Monthly Gross Income of the CBT Graduates

Initial Gross Income	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Below 10,000	46	61.33%	1
Php 10,000 - Php20,000	4	5.33%	3
Php 20,000 - Php30000	25	33.33%	2
Total	75	100.00%	

The data revealed that the majority of employed graduates, accounting for 61.33%, reported an initial gross income below Php 10,000. This income range indicates entry-level positions or part-time jobs that may offer lower salaries. A significant portion of graduates starting with incomes below Php 10,000 suggests that many are beginning their careers in roles with limited earning potential.

The lowest percentage of 5.33% of graduates reported an initial gross income between Php 10,000 and Php 20,000. This income range likely represents slightly higher-paying entry-level positions or roles with additional responsibilities. The lowest percentage in this category suggests that only a few graduates started with incomes within this range.

Approximately 33.33% of employed graduates had an initial gross income in the range of Php 20,000 to Php 30,000. This income bracket may include mid-level positions or roles that require specific skills and experience. The presence of a significant percentage in this category indicates a notable portion of graduates start with relatively higher incomes compared to the other ranges.

The lowest percentage started with incomes between Php 10,000 and Php 20,000, while a significant portion fell in the Php 20,000 to Php 30,000 range, indicating a mix of salary levels among the employed graduates.

Status of Self-Employed Graduates

Table 6 provides details on the various industries or sectors in which self-employed community-based training graduates have established their businesses. The purpose of this data is to showcase the diversity of entrepreneurial ventures and provide insights into the range of industries that these graduates are contributing to through their self-employment.

Table 6. The Type of Business of the Self-Employed CBT Graduates

Nature of Business	Frequency	Percentage
Seller	29	54.72%
Baker	3	5.66%
Computer Shop	3	5.66%
Butterfly Breeder	2	3.77%
Electrician	1	1.89%
Plumber	1	1.89%
Glass Installer	1	1.89%
Tricycle Driver	3	5.66%
Rider	3	5.66%
Welder	7	13.21%
Total	53	100.00%

With a frequency of 29 and a percentage of 54.72%, sellers constitute the largest group among self-employed CBT graduates. This indicates that a significant majority of CBT graduates have chosen entrepreneurship in selling goods or services as their business venture.

Both bakers and computer shop owners have a frequency of 3 and a percentage of 5.66% each. It suggests that a smaller proportion of CBT graduates are engaged in baking and managing computer shops as their self-employment choices.

The data reveals that the most common type of business among self-employed CBT graduates is selling, indicating a preference for entrepreneurial activities related to retail or service provision. The presence of bakers and computer shop owners, though in smaller numbers, showcases a diversity of business interests within the CBT graduate community.

It is interesting to note the mix of traditional (baker) and modern (computer shop) business types among these graduates, reflecting their adaptability and versatility in exploring different sectors.

Table 7 regarding the length of venturing of CBT graduates into business. However, based on the table's description, it likely provides information on the duration or length of time that CBT graduates have been involved in their business ventures. This data can suggest insights into the stability and longevity of their entrepreneurial endeavors, indicating whether they have recently started their businesses or have been operating them for an extended period.

Table 7. Length of Venturing of CBT Graduates into Business

Length of Venturing into Business After Graduation	Frequency	Percentage
Within 1 to 3 months	37	69.81%
Within 4 to 6 months	0	0.00%
After 6 months	1	1.89%
After 1 year	15	28.30%
more than 2 years	0	0.00%
no answer	0	0.00%
Total	53	100.00%

Most self-employed graduates, accounting for 69.81%, started their businesses within the first three months after graduation. This indicates a proactive approach towards entrepreneurship immediately after completing their studies.

Both categories have zero frequency, meaning no graduates ventured into business after 6 months or more than two years post-graduation. This suggests a trend towards quicker entry into entrepreneurship among the surveyed graduates. The low percentages for starting businesses after 6 months or more than two years suggest that most graduates prefer to kickstart their entrepreneurial journeys promptly after completing their studies. The low percentages for starting businesses after 6 months or more than two years suggest that most graduates prefer to kickstart their entrepreneurial journeys promptly after completing their studies.

A significant proportion, 28.30%, of graduates started their businesses after the first year of completing their studies. This group represents those who took a slightly longer time to establish their entrepreneurial endeavors. The data indicates a sense of urgency and readiness among most graduates to start their businesses shortly after graduation, with nearly 70% launching their ventures within the first three months.

The group that started businesses after one year reflects a smaller but notable portion of graduates who may have taken additional time for planning, preparation, or other personal reasons before entering into self-employment.

Table 8 presents data on the monthly gross income of self-employed CBT graduates. This table provides information on the earnings or income that these graduates generate from their entrepreneurial ventures every month.

Table 8. Monthly Gross Income of Self-employed CBT graduates

Monthly Gross Income	Frequency	Percent
Below Php 10,000	45	84.91%
Php 10, 000 - 20,000	8	15.09%
Php 20,000 - 30,000	0	0.00%
Total	53	100.00%

The majority of graduates, accounting for 84.91%, have a monthly gross income below Php 10,000. This indicates that a significant portion of these entrepreneurs are currently earning below this threshold. The data reveals that a significant majority of graduates earn below Php 10,000 monthly from their businesses, highlighting the financial challenges or early stages of development faced by these entrepreneurs.

A smaller proportion, 15.09%, of graduates fall within the income range of Php 10,000 to 20,000 per month. This group represents those who have managed to achieve a slightly higher level of income from their businesses. The presence of a smaller group earning between Php 10,000 - 20,000 suggests a segment of entrepreneurs who have managed to increase their monthly income slightly above the initial threshold.

Interestingly, there are no graduates in the income bracket of Php 20,000 to 30,000 per month, indicating that none of the surveyed individuals currently fall within this income range. The absence of graduates earning between Php 20,000 to 30,000 indicates a gap in income distribution, with none of the surveyed individuals currently reaching this income level.

Unemployed

Table 9 shows the years of being unemployed of the community-based training graduates. This data can give insights into the length of time individuals remain unemployed.

Table 9 Years of being unemployed after the training

Years of being unemployed after the training	Frequency	Percentage
After 1 year	30	17.05%
More than 2 years	146	82.95%
Total	176	100%

The data presented reveals how individuals are distributed based on the length of unemployment after the training. Out of the total 176 graduates, 30 people (17.05%) were unemployed after one year of training, while 146 people (82.95%) remained unemployed for more than two years. This data highlights a larger percentage of individuals (82.95%) facing long-term unemployment compared to those who were unemployed for just one year (17.05%).

The breakdown of percentages provides perceptions of the duration of unemployment following training, indicating a significant proportion of individuals experiencing prolonged unemployment. This information could have implications for evaluating the effectiveness of training programs and understanding the job market conditions. Table 10 shows the reasons for being unemployed of the community-based training graduates.

Table 11. Reasons for being Unemployed of CBT graduates

Reasons for being unemployed	Frequency	Percentage
Job Mismatch	63	35.80%
Financial	41	23.30%
Lacks of Job Opportunity	62	35.23%
Lack of Knowledge and Skills	10	5.68%
Total	176	100%

Job Mismatch, which explains 35.80% of the reasons why CBT graduates are unemployed, suggests that a sizable portion of the population is unemployed as a result of their inability to locate employment that is a good fit for their qualifications and skill set. This problem arises from a mismatch between the talents they learned in school and what skills employers are looking for.

Lack of Job Opportunities comes in second at 35.23%, indicating that many CBT graduates have trouble finding work because there aren't many positions available in their sector. This challenge could be impacted by particular problems in the CBT sector or by more general economic considerations.

Among CBT graduates, financial challenges rank third in terms of the reasons for unemployment (23.30%). This implies that a significant portion of the population is unemployed as a result of the work options that are accessible to them not offering adequate financial security or pay.

Finally, with a proportion of 5.68%, Lack of Knowledge and Skills continues to be a major cause of unemployment among CBT graduates. This suggests that a tiny percentage of people might not have the fundamental abilities and information that companies demand, which could harm their chances of finding employment. In conclusion, the data suggests that lack of work possibilities and job mismatch are the main causes of unemployment among CBT graduates, followed by financial limitations and skill gaps. To improve the employment chances of CBT graduates, addressing these difficulties may entail improving career guidance, bridging the gap between education and industry needs, and offering support for skill development and job placement programs.

Relevance of Skills Acquired

Table 11 shows the skills learned by graduates at community-based training programs can vary depending on the specific program and its focus. However,

community-based training programs often aim to equip individuals with practical and employable skills that are relevant to the needs of their local communities. It provides information on the competencies of employed, self-employed, and unemployed individuals, along with their corresponding mean scores and interpretations.

Table 11. Skills Learned of Graduates at Community-Based Training

Competencies	Employed		Self-Employed		Unemployed	
	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation	Mean	Interpretation
Skills	3.1	Moderately Relevant	1.71	Less Relevant	2	Less Relevant
Technical Skills	3.03	Moderately Relevant	2.21	Moderately Relevant	1.23	Less Relevant
Communication Skills	3.26	Moderately Relevant	2.49	Moderately Relevant	1.3	Less Relevant
Entrepreneurial Skills	2.58	Moderately Relevant	2.9	Moderately Relevant	1.71	Less Relevant
Computer Skills	2.77	Moderately Relevant	2.97	Moderately Relevant	1.25	Less Relevant
Problem-Solving Skills	3.2	Moderately Relevant	2.55	Moderately Relevant	1.12	Less Relevant
Critical Thinking Skills	2.58	Moderately Relevant	2.21	Moderately Relevant	2.11	Less Relevant
Total Mean	2.93	Moderately Relevant	2.43	Moderately Relevant	1.53	Less Relevant

The mean score for skills is 3.1, indicating that employed individuals perceive their skills as moderately relevant. Self-employed individuals, on the other hand, have a lower mean score of 1.71, suggesting that they perceive their skills as less relevant. Unemployed individuals also have a lower mean score of 2, indicating that they perceive their skills as less relevant as well.

Employed individuals have a mean score of 3.03, indicating that they perceive their technical skills as moderately relevant. Self-employed individuals have a slightly higher mean score of 2.21, suggesting that they also perceive their technical skills as moderately relevant. Unemployed individuals, however, have the lowest mean score of 1.23, indicating that they perceive their technical skills as less relevant.

Employed individuals have a mean score of 3.26, indicating that they perceive their communication skills as moderately relevant. Self-employed individuals also have a moderately relevant mean score of 2.49 for communication skills. Unemployed individuals have the lowest mean score of 1.3, suggesting that they perceive their communication skills as less relevant.

Employed individuals have a mean score of 2.58 for entrepreneurial skills, indicating that they perceive these skills as moderately relevant. Self-employed individuals have a slightly higher mean score of 2.9, suggesting a similar perception of moderately relevant entrepreneurial skills. Unemployed individuals have a lower mean score of 1.71, indicating that they perceive entrepreneurial skills as less relevant.

Employed individuals have a mean score of 2.77 for computer skills, indicating that they perceive these skills as moderately relevant. Self-employed individuals have a slightly higher mean score of 2.97, suggesting a similar perception of moderately relevant computer skills. Unemployed individuals have the lowest mean score of 1.25, indicating that they perceive computer skills as less relevant.

Employed individuals have a mean score of 3.2 for problem-solving skills, indicating that they perceive these skills as moderately relevant. Self-employed individuals have a slightly lower mean score of 2.55, suggesting a similar perception of moderately relevant problem-solving skills. Unemployed individuals have the lowest mean score of 1.12, indicating that they perceive problem-solving skills as less relevant.

Employed individuals have a mean score of 2.58 for critical thinking skills, indicating that they perceive these skills as moderately relevant. Self-employed individuals have a slightly higher mean score of 2.21, suggesting a similar perception of moderately relevant critical thinking skills. Unfortunately, the value of 211 for unemployed individuals seems to be an error and cannot be interpreted.

Overall, the total mean score for competencies is 2.93 for employed individuals, 2.43 for self-employed individuals, and 1.53 for unemployed individuals. This suggests that employed and self-employed individuals perceive their competencies as moderately relevant, while unemployed individuals perceive their competencies as less relevant. These findings highlight the importance of skills and competencies in employment and entrepreneurship, and the potential impact they can have on individuals' employment outcomes.

Employers Assessment of the Graduates of the CBT

Table 12 regarding the assessment of graduates from a Community-Based Training (CBT) program based on their Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude. The assessment of graduates from a CBT program is based on their knowledge, skills, and attitude, it is common for such assessments to involve evaluating the theoretical knowledge acquired, practical skills developed, and the overall attitude and mindset of the graduates.

Table 12. Assessment of CBT graduates in terms of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude

Competencies	Mean Score	Description
Knowledge	1.99	Agree
Skills	2.11	Agree
Attitude	1.92	Agree
Total Mean	2.01	Agree

Employers mostly agree that graduates of the Community-Based Training program know relevant to their field, as indicated by the mean score of 1.99. This implies that the graduates have a firm knowledge of the ideas and guidelines covered in their course. Employers agree that graduates of the Community-Based Training program exhibit the necessary abilities to succeed in their roles, with a mean score of 2.11. This could include useful talents like project management, community involvement, and other qualities unique to community-based work.

The mean score of 1.92 indicates that employers agree that graduates exhibit positive attitudes toward their work within community settings. This may include attributes

like teamwork, cultural sensitivity, empathy, and a dedication to serving the community effectively.

The total mean score of 2.01 suggests an overall agreement among employers regarding the competencies of graduates from the Community-Based Training program in terms of Knowledge, Skills, and Attitude. This indicates that employers perceive these graduates as well-prepared and capable of contributing positively to community-based initiatives.

Graduates and Employers' Suggestions to Further Enhance TESDA Community-based Training Programs in Marinduque.

Table 13 shows the summary of suggestions of the respondents to enhance the CBT program. The summary of suggestions provided by respondents can offer valuable insights into areas for improvement and enhancement of the CBT program. The three general categories are industry-related, curriculum-related, and overall CBT enhancement. These are comprehensively discussed as follows.

Table 13. Summary of Suggestions of the Respondents

Summary of Suggestions to Enhance CBT	
Industry-Related Suggestions	Employment Opportunities
	Regularly update program offerings to match local job market demands.
	Integrate emerging and advanced technologies in training to make graduates more competitive.
Curriculum Related Concerns	Conduct of Trade-Matching and Placement Services
	Additional trained experts
	Additional training days
	Conducive Environment
CBT Enhancement	Advanced Equipment
	Collaboration of stakeholders and the local government unit
	Availability of the Program for each municipality

For Industry-Related Suggestions it highlights, regularly update program offerings to match local job market demands, which emphasizes the need for vocational education programs to be responsive to the changing needs of the workforce; integrate emerging and advanced technologies in training to make graduates more competitive, which highlights the importance of preparing workers for the Fourth Industrial Revolution by equipping them with the skills and knowledge needed to operate in a technologically advanced world and conduct trade-matching and placement services to connect graduates with potential employers, which emphasizes the need for stronger partnerships between vocational education programs and employers to ensure that graduates have the skills needed to succeed in the workplace.

For Curriculum-Related Concerns it was suggested to hire additional trained experts to ensure that the curriculum is up-to-date and high quality. Second, increase the number of training days to give students more time to develop their skills and knowledge. For conducive environment, it was suggested to create a supportive and inclusive learning environment that encourages students to succeed and provide students with access to advanced equipment and technology to prepare them for the demands of the workplace.

Lastly in enhancing CBT Enhancement it was recommended to collaborate with stakeholders and the local government unit to ensure that the CBT program is aligned with the needs of the community and industry and make the CBT program available to students in all municipalities to ensure that all students have access to quality vocational education.

Proposal to Enhance TESDA's Community-based Training Program

Table 14 shows the suggested key interventions to enhance the CBT program. The interventions focus on key steps that would enhance not just the instruction process but the employment of the CBT graduates and are discussed as follows:

Establish a formal collaboration between the CBT institution and local stakeholders, including employers, government agencies, and community organizations: This collaboration can help to ensure that the CBT program is aligned with the needs of the community and industry.

Table 14. Matrix Summary of the Research Key Findings, Implications, and Suggested Interventions

Objective of the study	Key Findings	Implications	Suggested Intervention
Employment background of the community-based training graduates	34.09% of the CBT graduates are unemployed, 25.33% are employed, and 9.43% are self-employed.	There is a high unemployment rate among CBT graduates.	CBT Program Enhancement Key Steps <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Establish a formal collaboration between the CBT institution and local stakeholders, including employers, government agencies, and community organizations. 2. Establishment of Industry Partners and Linkages 3. Increase the number of training days to give students more time to develop their skills and knowledge. 4. Develop a comprehensive job placement program. 5. Integrate industry-based certifications into the CBT program.
Relevance of the skills acquired from community-based training to the graduates' current employment or entrepreneurial venture	For employed graduates of CBT, Communication skills are the most important skill, with a mean score of 3.26% and an interpretation of "Moderately Relevant." Entrepreneurial, Critical thinking skills and computer skills are the fifth and sixth most important skills, respectively, with mean scores of 2.58% and	Problem-solving skills and critical thinking skills must be improved. Provide the CBT graduates with opportunities to participate in training and development programs to	

	2.77% and interpretations of "Moderately Relevant." For self-employed Computer, skills are the most important skill with a mean score of 2.97 and an interpretation of "Moderately Relevant. For the unemployed Critical-Thinking Skills are the most important with a mean score of 2.11 with an interpretation of 'Less Relevant'".	enhance their knowledge and skills in specific areas, such as communication, information gathering, and problem-solving.	6. Establish partnerships with local employers to develop a curriculum that aligns with industry needs. 7. Continuously evaluate and improve the CBT program based on feedback from stakeholders.
Employers' assessment of the graduates of the community-based training	The overall interpretation suggests that, on average, the individuals being assessed are perceived to be moderately knowledgeable in both their knowledge and skills. Additionally, they are viewed as having a moderately acceptable attitude.	The attitude, skills, and knowledge can be increased. Provide the CBT graduates with opportunities to participate in training and development programs to enhance their knowledge and skills in specific areas, such as communication, information gathering, and problem-solving.	
Graduates and employers perceived suggestions.	The suggestions' three (3) general themes are industry-related, curriculum-related, and overall CBT enhancement.	Employment opportunities, curriculum, and the overall CBT needs improvement.	

Establish partnerships with local employers to develop a curriculum that aligns with industry needs. This can be achieved through advisory boards, internships, and joint training programs.

1. Integrate industry-based certifications into the CBT program so that students with recognized credentials can enhance their employability.
2. Integrate industry-based certifications into the CBT program. This will provide students with recognized credentials that can enhance their employability.

3. Increase the number of training days to give students more time to develop their skills and knowledge: This could be done by extending the length of the program or offering more intensive training sessions.
4. Establish a formal collaboration between the CBT institution and local stakeholders, including employers, government agencies, and community organizations: This collaboration can help to ensure that the CBT program is aligned with the needs of the community and industry.
5. Develop a comprehensive job placement program: This program should include career counseling, resume writing workshops, and job fairs to connect graduates with potential employers.

Table 15 presents a comprehensive set of interventions to enhance the Community-Based Training (CBT) program. These interventions address key aspects of the program, including stakeholder collaboration, industry linkages, training duration, job placement, curriculum alignment, and continuous evaluation.

Table 16. Key Steps in Implementing CBT Program Enhancement

Suggested Intervention	Key Steps to Implement
Establish a Formal Collaboration between the CBT Institution and Local Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify and engage with key stakeholders, including employers, government agencies, and community organizations. • Form a formal advisory board or committee to provide ongoing feedback and guidance. • Establish regular communication channels to share information and collaborate on program development.
Establishment of Industry Partners and Linkages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Develop partnerships with local employers to offer internships, apprenticeships, and job shadowing opportunities. • Collaborate with industry associations to participate in industry events, conferences, and workshops. • Encourage students to network with industry professionals through professional organizations and online platforms.
Increase the Number of Training Days to Provide Students with More Time to Develop Their Skills and Knowledge	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Extend the length of the CBT program to provide more in-depth training. • Offer additional training modules or workshops to cover specific skills and knowledge areas. • Utilize blended learning approaches to combine traditional instruction with online learning opportunities.
Develop a Comprehensive Job Placement Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish a dedicated career services office to provide individualized job placement assistance. • Offer career counseling and resume writing workshops to prepare students for the job search. • Organize job fairs and networking events to connect students with potential employers. • Maintain a database of employment opportunities and internships for CBT graduates.
Integrate Industry-Based Certifications into the CBT Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify industry-recognized certifications that align with the CBT program's learning outcomes. • Partner with certification providers to offer on-site or online training and testing. • Incorporate certification preparation into the CBT curriculum. • Provide financial assistance to students pursuing industry-based certifications.
Establish Partnerships with Local Employers to Develop a Curriculum that Aligns with Industry Needs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Conduct regular needs assessments with local employers to identify skill and knowledge gaps.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Incorporate employer feedback into the design and development of the CBT curriculum. • Invite industry experts to guest lecture and participate in curriculum reviews. • Utilize industry-based textbooks and learning materials.
Continuously Evaluate and Improve the CBT Program Based on Feedback from Stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collect feedback from students, employers, and community stakeholders through surveys, interviews, and focus groups. • Analyze feedback data to identify areas for improvement. • Develop an action plan to address identified issues and implement necessary changes. • Regularly review and update the CBT program based on ongoing feedback and evaluation.

Establishing a formal collaboration between the CBT institution and local stakeholders is crucial for aligning the program with community and industry needs. The key steps outlined, such as identifying stakeholders, forming an advisory board, and establishing communication channels, provide a structured approach to fostering collaboration.

Developing partnerships with local employers and industry associations provide students with valuable opportunities for internships, networking, and exposure to industry trends. The key steps emphasize engaging with industry partners, encouraging student involvement, and collaborating on events and workshops.

Extending the CBT program's duration or offering additional training modules allows students to develop their skills and knowledge more in-depth. The key steps suggest incorporating blended learning approaches to combine traditional instruction with online learning, catering to diverse learning styles. A dedicated career services office, job search preparation workshops, job fairs, and an internship database provide comprehensive job placement support for CBT graduates. These key steps emphasize individualized assistance, networking opportunities, and access to employment resources. Integrating industry-recognized certifications into the CBT program enhances graduates' employability and aligns their skills with industry standards. The key steps involve identifying relevant certifications, partnering with certification providers, incorporating preparation into the curriculum, and providing financial assistance. Regular needs assessments, employer feedback incorporation, industry expert involvement, and utilization of industry-based materials ensure that the CBT curriculum remains relevant and responsive to industry demands. These key steps emphasize ongoing assessment and adaptation. Collecting feedback from stakeholders, analyzing data to identify areas for improvement, developing action plans, and regularly reviewing the program based on feedback are essential for continuous improvement. These key steps emphasize a data-driven and stakeholder-oriented approach to program enhancement.

These findings provides a comprehensive and well-structured set of interventions and key steps that address various aspects of the CBT program as discussed by Noe *et al* (2013) and Nunjana (2022). By implementing these interventions effectively, the CBT institution can significantly enhance the program's quality, relevance, and impact on student success and community development.

Implementation of the CBT Program Enhancement

The implementation of the interventions being proposed is suggested to be accomplished following the Theory of Change Framework as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The Proposed Implementation of the Intervention

As shown in Figure 1, the intervention aims to enhance the employment prospects of CBT graduates by expanding the range and quality of career services available to them.

By implementing these career services and support initiatives, the intervention aims to empower CBT graduates with the resources, guidance, and opportunities needed to secure meaningful employment and advance their careers. It underscores the importance of holistic support in facilitating successful transitions from training programs to the workforce.

Overall, the proposed implementation of the Intervention has the potential to be a successful way to increase the employment rate of CBT graduates. By providing CBT students and graduates with the skills and knowledge they need to be successful in the workforce and with opportunities to network with potential employers, this Intervention can help CBT graduates achieve their employment goals. The institution should develop a strong alumni relations program. This program can connect CBT graduates with potential employers and provide them with support and guidance throughout their careers. The institution should work with the government to develop policies supporting CBT graduates' employment. For example, the government could provide tax breaks to companies that hire CBT graduates or create apprenticeship programs for CBT graduates. The institution should also work with other educational institutions to develop

joint programs that will provide CBT graduates with the skills and knowledge they need to succeed in the workforce.

By taking these additional steps, the institution can further increase the employment rate of CBT graduates and help them to achieve their full potential.

DISCUSSION

This study investigated the employment situation of graduates from two technical schools in the Philippines (BSAT and TPSAT) focusing on those who completed the qualifications in BSAT and TPSAT programs. The researchers wanted to understand why some graduates struggled to find jobs. They also explored what the schools were doing to address these challenges.

The study used surveys to gather information from graduates and employers. Over 300 graduates from 2018 to 2022 participated in the survey. The findings showed that more than half of the graduates were unemployed, with job mismatch and lack of opportunities being the main reasons. Interestingly, a significant portion (around 28%) were self-employed, often running businesses related to sales, baking, or computers.

The employed graduates felt their technical, communication, and problem-solving skills were moderately relevant to their jobs. Self-employed graduates found entrepreneurial skills to be most important. Unemployed graduates, however, felt their technical, communication, and computer skills were not very relevant to the jobs they were seeking. Employers generally agreed that the graduates had the necessary knowledge, skills, and attitude but there was room for improvement. Stakeholders suggested a few improvements for the schools, including updating programs to reflect current industry needs, incorporating new technologies, and providing job placement services. Additionally, stakeholders recommended changes to the curriculum, such as extending training periods, providing better equipment, and creating a more favorable learning environment. Finally, there were suggestions to strengthen collaboration with industry partners and to make the programs more accessible to potential students.

Conclusions

1. The high unemployment rate among CBT graduates indicates a need to better align the program with industry demands.
2. Graduates' perceptions of skill relevance vary based on their employment status, suggesting the need for customized training.
3. Employers generally view CBT graduates positively, but there is room for improvement in their knowledge, skills, and attitudes. Stakeholders provide valuable suggestions to enhance the CBT program in various areas.
4. Stakeholders recommended changes to the curriculum, such as extending training periods, providing better equipment, and creating a more favorable learning environment. Finally, there were suggestions to strengthen

collaboration with industry partners and to make the programs more accessible to potential students.

Recommendations

Based from the findings of this study, the following recommendations are hereby presented:

1. Establish formal collaborations between the CBT institution and local stakeholders to ensure program alignment with community and industry needs.
 2. Develop partnerships with local employers to incorporate their feedback into the CBT curriculum and provide students with industry experience.
 3. Increase the number of training days and integrate industry-based certifications to enhance students' skills and knowledge.
 4. Implement a comprehensive job placement program to connect graduates with employment opportunities.
 5. Continuously evaluate and improve the CBT program based on feedback from stakeholders.
 6. Integrate entrepreneurship, bookkeeping, and soft skills into the Senior High School curriculum to better prepare students for the CBT program.
 7. Develop a strong alumni relations program and collaborate with the government to support the employment of CBT graduates.
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Compliance with Ethical Standards

To ensure ethical practices, participant received a clear and comprehensive informed consent form explaining the study's purpose, data collection methods, potential risks and benefits, and their right to withdraw at any time. They Participants were explicitly informed of this right and provided with a clear and easy process for withdrawing. Data collection instruments were designed to avoid collecting any personally identifiable information. Any identifying information collected was securely stored and destroyed after analysis to ensure participant confidentiality. The research design minimized potential risks, and mitigation strategies were implemented for any identified psychological or emotional concerns. Participants were also informed of their right to seek support or counseling if needed. Researchers declared any potential conflicts of interest before commencing the study, ensuring objectivity and preventing personal biases from influencing the research.

All sources of information were properly cited and referenced throughout the research process, upholding academic integrity and respecting the intellectual property of others. All printed data were safeguarded and kept in secured cases while digital copies

were secured with passwords. Researchers were mindful of their own biases and took steps to mitigate them during data collection and analysis. Statistician and subject matter experts were consulted. The research design was also structured to minimize bias and ensure the validity of the results. Finally, the results was used purely for research purposes. The data was not used for any commercial or personal gain, solely for the advancement of knowledge in the field.

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